

Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation (IDEAS-QA4EO) Phase 2 WP2170 Snow Studies Final Report

IDEAS-QA4EO

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1. Introduction

This document is the final report for the activities in WP2170 (Snow Studies) of IDEAS-QA4EO Framework Phase 2, covering between March 2022 and November 2024. The work package aims to develop and study innovative methods to validate satellite derived snow cover products, using fit-for-purpose reference data. The work has started in the previous framework of IDEAS+ and progressed in this framework. Previously, imagery from Finnish camera networks were used to produce snow cover data using statistics-based algorithm and then the produced data was used in near real-time (NRT) comparison with some of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) snow cover products. A single platform on a single virtual machine included all the components. In this framework, the reference data was extended to Northern hemisphere coverage, including webcam imagery from Phenocam Network and in-situ snow depth data from WMO network. Two machine learning models, developed in FMI, are used to produce snow cover data from the extensive collection of webcam imagery. Additional satellite derived products are added to the system, which has undergone extensive improvements in backend and frontend components. The Cal/Val part of the system (FMI ARKSATQA Portal, arksatqa.fmi.fi) was separated from the webcam data processing system (FMIPROT and Camera Network Portal, fmiprot.fmi.fi).

The period focused on improving methodologies for cross-validation, incorporating cutting-edge machine learning techniques, optimizing system capabilities, and expanding the range of validation efforts both geographically and temporally. The overarching goal was to ensure that the system could meet the growing demands of snow cover monitoring and validation in an increasingly data-driven and interconnected research landscape. During this timeframe, the project achieved significant milestones, addressing challenges related to scalability, data diversity, and methodological robustness. These achievements enabled the cal/val platform to transition into a state-of-the-art tool that seamlessly integrates data from a variety of sources, including webcams, satellite products, and in-situ observations, for comprehensive snow cover validation. By leveraging the latest technologies, the project has set a benchmark for snow cover monitoring systems.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Camera networks and webcam imagery

In the work package, webcam imagery from environmental camera networks are used:

- MONIMET Camera Network consists of 30+ cameras (some of them not working any more) in Finland, installed by MONIMET project consortium. The data is managed by FMI. Images are freely available, annually updated in Zenodo and in NRT via FTP accounts created by FMI. [1,2]
- FMI Cameras in automatic weather stations: These cameras are managed by FMI, providing imagery of instruments, fields and snow turfs. The temporal extent of the images differs, but mostly available up to 1 year. Some of those images are archived in FMIPROT platform but only intended for FMI use. Snow cover information produced from the images is freely available, but images are not accessible from outside.
- Airport cameras in Finland: FMI also has access to some cameras in Finnish airports. The temporal extent of the images differs, but mostly available up to 1 year. Some of those images are archived in FMIPROT platform but only intended for FMI use. Snow cover information produced from the images is freely available, but images are not accessible from outside.
- The PhenoCam Network is a collaborative, continental-scale observatory that employs networked digital cameras to monitor vegetation phenology across various ecosystems in North America and globally. Established in 2008, PhenoCam now encompasses more than 700 sites and boasts an image archive exceeding 60 million photos. These images and associated data are freely accessible in near-real time through the official website. FMIPROT has the capability to scan the website and retrieve the images. [3]

2.2. FMIPROT Software

FMI Image Processing Toolbox (FMIPROT) is software designed to process digital image series from cameras and camera networks. It can acquire and process images from multiple camera networks on a single platform by adding connection information of the image repositories. It provides a graphical user interface to set up configurations and parameters to be used in the acquisition and processing of the images. The analysis can be run either using the GUI or via CLI with a single action that triggers a processing chain. The toolbox performs necessary tasks to acquire images from image repositories of the camera networks, process them and generate HTML reports with interactive plots along for

visualization of the output data. The design allows using the toolbox with a job scheduler to run analysis for creating operational monitoring systems. FMIPROT is open source and freely available as described in the license. [4,5,6]

2.3. Fractional snow cover by adaptive thresholding

The snow detection algorithm classifies pixels in an image as snow-covered or snow-free by analyzing the histogram of the blue channel. A threshold value is determined by identifying the first local minimum in the histogram above a digital number (DN) of 127, with DN 127 used as a default when no local minimum is found. Pixels with blue channel values above the threshold are classified as snow-covered. The histogram is calculated only for the region of interest (ROI) and smoothed by averaging nearby data points. Once classified, the image undergoes orthorectification, aligning it with real-world coordinates using digital elevation models (DEM) and unit vectors that define the camera's viewing geometry. (The orthorectification part is not applied for most cameras, as the field of view is too close.) This process involves correcting for radial lens distortion, mapping the DEM to camera coordinates, applying perspective projection, and scaling the data to the image size. The resulting georeferenced snow cover map is used to calculate fractional snow cover (FSC) by counting snow-covered and snow-free pixels within the ROI. This method was tested on mountain images from the Alps and southern Italy and adapted for boreal environments, including forests and wetlands [4,7]. This method was also studied in the context of providing snow cover status as an auxiliary information to snow depth observations, which has low quality when it is lower than 2 cm [8]. The algorithm is implemented in FMIPROT software, available freely.

2.4. Snow cover by machine learning models

Our recent [8] and previous [7] studies show that the adaptive thresholding method provides continuous, reliable information under certain conditions, but it is not reliable enough to be used with a high number of cameras, without checking the conditions. Also, a ROI should be defined to restrict the processing to a suitable portion of the image. To be able to use all the cameras available, a more generalizable method is required. The method should be able to either detect the areas or textures in the image relevant to snow or be as independent from the conditions and a ROI. Previously in another project, multiple deep learning models (3 artificial neural network (ANN) and 3 convolutional neural network (CNN) models) to obtain snow cover information are developed and tested using imagery from Finnish airport cameras, FMI AWS cameras and MONIMET cameras. Manually generated reference data using the pictures are used for training the models. Unlike the

adaptive thresholding method, the models do not provide fractional snow cover (0-100%) but instead, they are created using 3 classes of snow cover: No-snow, partial snow and full snow. Two best of those models, according to prediction accuracy (between 84% - 97%), are chosen to be used in FMIPROT & Camera Network Portal. The models are applied on all the cameras available, thus a core part of the overall system. FMIPROT setups are created by scripts, rather than manually setting. This is possible because the models do not need ROI selection, instead, they are using the whole image. The models are used by FMIPROT as a plugin (which is wrapped in the format FMIPROT accepts), rather than implementing it in FMIPROT code, because the models are not usable by Python 2, but only Python 3. A detailed report on the developed models is provided to ESA as an attachment to this report but not published inside this document and not publicly available.

2.5. NRT webcam data processing and FMIPROT & Camera Network Portal

The platform to run FMIPROT for NRT processing of webcam imagery was previously set up and improved. The platform consists of a virtual machine with web hosting capabilities and access to the internet and FMI internal network. FMIPROT software is installed on the VM and various wrappers, a custom job scheduler, a simple data API and the Camera Network Portal webpage is created. Several components are working together, which in result, acquiring webcam imagery from different sources of webcam data, processing them according to FMIPROT setups by triggers from the job scheduler and finally hosting the results as raw data and web-based reports with plots. The data API provides the resulting webcam derived data according to several options selected by users. It is used in the NRT comparison platform to acquire webcam derived data to be compared with the satellite products.

All the components of the portal are improved in the reported period. Some of the components and features are developed in the reported period. Additionally, the processing setups are reorganized to handle vast amounts of data processing, along with some architectural updates in FMIPROT.

2.6. Satellite derived snow cover products

Following products are used in the cal/val platform, compared with the webcam derived and in-situ snow cover data:

- CLMS Snow Cover Extent Northern Hemisphere 1 km resolution [9]
- CLMS Snow Cover Extent Pan-European 500m resolution [9]
- CLMS High Resolution Snow and Ice (HRSI) Fractional Snow Cover [9]

- CLMS HRSI Daily Cumulative Gap-filled Fractional Snow Cover [9]
- EUMETSAT H SAF H12 Effective snow cover by VIS/IR radiometry Pan-Europe [10]
- EUMETSAT HSAF H34 Snow detection (snow mask) by VIS/IR radiometry covering full MSG Disk [10]
- EUMETSAT HSAF H35 Effective snow cover by VIS/IR radiometry Northern Hemisphere [10]
- EUMETSAT HSAF H43 Snow extent (snow mask) by VIS/NIR of MTG FCI (Not operational) [10]

The products are accessed using CLMS API and FMI internal network. The EUMETSAT products are added in the reported period.

2.7. NRT Comparisons and FMI ARKSATQA Portal

The platform to run the comparison of satellite derived products and the reference data (webcam derived and in-situ) is developed in the framework. The platform consists of a virtual machine with web hosting capabilities and access to the internet and FMI internal network. A custom scheduler, similar to the one in FMIPROT platform, is regularly running python-based comparison scripts which acquires the reference data and satellite-based products from various sources, obtaining corresponding value pairs to be compared. The value pairs are then stored in CSV files for the web-based application to be used in the calculation of the performance metrics and the creation of interactive maps, according to the comparison options selected by the user. There is a comparison script and job for each type of reference data (in-situ and webcam derived), for each satellite product. Although the scripts are separate, they follow the same architecture, which is swift to adapt to a newly added product for each case.

The interface of the web page includes various options for the user to calculate comparison metrics and include/exclude data according to temporal extent and webcam processing algorithm. Additionally, for the comparisons using webcam derived data, multicategory contingency matrices are available according to the selection by the user.

All the components of the portal are developed in the reported period.

2.8. Overall processing system structure

All the components of the processing systems used in the work package and the data flow between them are illustrated in Figure 1. below.

Figure 1: Components of the overall system, consisting of FMIPROT & Camera Network Portal, FMI ARKSATQA Portal, FMI data network and external data access

3. Key Achievements and challenges

The scope of data sources was significantly broadened during this period. The FMIPROT system integrated data from over 400 webcams, expanding its geographical coverage to include North America, Europe, and select regions in Asia and Oceania, such as China and New Zealand. These new additions enhanced the diversity of the dataset, enabling more robust cross-validation efforts. Additionally, satellite snow cover products from EUMETSAT HSAF (H12, H34, H35, and H43) and CLMS HRSI (FSC and GFSC) were incorporated. The inclusion of the H43 product marked the system's first "Day-1 validation," demonstrating its ability to validate pre-operational satellite products. In-situ observations spanning nine years were also added, providing a critical layer of ground truth data to support validation across multiple continents.

Another major focus of the project was the implementation of machine learning algorithms to improve snow cover detection and analysis. The adaptive thresholding method of snow detection relied on fixed algorithms with limited adaptability to diverse conditions. To overcome this, machine learning techniques were introduced to analyze images and detect snow presence in webcam imagery more accurately. Initial results from the ML implementations were highly promising, prompting the team to assess it further and document their findings in a scientific article currently under preparation.

The simple but effective data API developed in FMIPROT & Camera Network Portal is one of the features that can be used by users. Using the API, one can download the webcam derived data programmatically, according to selected options and create their own validation schemes.

The QA Portal, the primary interface for users to access and analyze data, was significantly enhanced. New visualization tools, such as RMSE maps, scatter plots, and detailed performance metrics, were added to provide deeper insights into the validation process. The interactive features of the portal allowed users to filter and explore data by specific algorithms, temporal ranges, and data sources. This flexibility was particularly valuable for researchers conducting targeted analyses. Additional metadata, such as geolocation extent information, was integrated into the system to enrich the validation context, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing snow cover accuracy.

One of the accomplishments was the integration of geolocation metadata into FMIPROT's processing system. This enhancement addressed long-standing geospatial challenges by improving the accuracy of comparisons between webcam-derived data and satellite

imagery. Previously, the system relied on a simplistic approach that used camera locations as the reference point for comparisons. However, this method often failed in cases where the camera's field of view encompassed distant or complex terrains. By incorporating geolocation metadata, the system could now define and use precise regions of interest (ROIs), including polygon-based definitions, for better alignment with satellite data. These updates were particularly beneficial for cameras located in mountainous areas, where snow cover data is critical yet challenging to validate.

The project's findings and progress were disseminated widely during this period, ensuring that the advancements reached both the scientific community and operational stakeholders. Presentations at major international conferences, including the ESA Living Planet Symposium 2022, the EUMETSAT Meteorological Satellite Conference 2024 and the LPVE Workshop 2023, highlighted the system's capabilities and findings. Regular updates were also shared at Cal/Val Workshops, fostering collaboration and feedback from global experts. These dissemination efforts not only validated the project's significance but also established FMIPROT as a leading tool for webcam-based snow cover validation research. An abstract was also sent for ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025.

Several challenges were addressed successfully over the course of this period. The growing scale of data posed a significant hurdle, requiring innovative solutions to ensure efficient processing and storage. By implementing caching mechanisms and optimizing processing chains, the team resolved these challenges, enabling the system to handle large datasets with minimal latency. To handle the growing scale of data, FMIPROT software and the processing platform underwent a comprehensive optimization process. The system faced challenges related to disk space limitations and slow data retrieval times, particularly as the number of cameras and datasets increased. These issues were resolved through the development of microservices for caching image data, which resulted in a tenfold improvement in query speeds. By adopting modular and scalable design principles, FMIPROT & Camera Network Portal became capable of processing vast datasets from hundreds of webcams across multiple years, ensuring that it could keep pace with the project's expansion goals. Geospatial complexities, particularly in aligning satellite and webcam data, were another critical issue. The integration of geolocation metadata proved instrumental in overcoming these challenges, allowing for precise comparisons even in complex terrains. Additionally, the diversity of datasets, which included different camera networks, satellite products, and in-situ observations, necessitated a flexible and adaptable approach. The integration of machine learning techniques provided the required adaptability, enabling the system to manage and analyze diverse datasets effectively.

4. Future work

The Cal/Val and FMIPROT platforms developed during this period demonstrate the capability to process large volumes of webcam data and leverage multi-year in-situ observations for near-real-time (NRT) comparisons with satellite-based snow products. However, several aspects of the system require further development, refinement, and expansion to enhance their operational readiness and scalability. Additionally, the training extent, thus the real performance of the ML method can make the comparisons questionable. For this to be known, the methods should be assessed in a broader context, weak points should be determined and if necessary, a new method should be developed. Only after these critical improvements are addressed can the platforms be considered fully operational for maintaining and improving satellite-based snow cover products.

The following tasks have been identified as priorities for future work:

- Assess the current ML models in the system
- Create a new ML model or ML models which can be used with cameras from different types of climates, topography and field of view
- Publish the results of the ML assessment and/or developments
- Investigate the accessibility of in-situ snow state ground observations (multiclass snow cover information) and integrate it to the system
- Replace satellite-based product data ingestion method to use products official dissemination channel (e.g. use H SAF FTP instead of FMI internal network)
- Review comparison platform architecture from modularity perspective, with aim to swiftly extent product availability and integration
- Integrate more satellite-based products, e.g. MODIS snow products and “Copernicus Land Monitoring Service High Resolution Water Snow and Ice” products (which is becoming soon operational), H SAF H85 (in development)
- Investigate new data curation and processing methods, e.g. digital twins and GPU based and microservices based computing architecture

By addressing these tasks, the platforms can evolve into robust tools for operational use, supporting the continuous improvement of satellite-based snow cover products and advancing our understanding of their performance.

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